

Patent

Prerequisite: 3
unshared projects

Fame: 1
Draw 3 cards

Review

a covered project
becomes open

If false: Fame 1

Review

a covered project
becomes open

If false: Fame 1

Foreign teaching

Prerequisite:
Fame 10

Draw 1 card
Do another action

Teaching in a PhD course

Prerequisite:
1 «Foreign teaching»
and 3 «Invited
speaker»

Take 1 upgrade

Fame: 3

Editor in chief

Prerequisite:
you played at least
3 Reviews

Draw 1 more card
each turn

Fame: 2

Patent

Prerequisite: 3
unshared projects

Fame: 1
Draw 3 cards

Review

a covered project
becomes open

If False: Fame 1

Review

a covered project
becomes open

If False: Fame 1

